

NOT KNOWLEDGE OF PROFESSIONAL VOCABULARY IS THE REASON FOR STUDENTS' FAIL

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Annotation: The article tells about the enrichment of the vocabulary in the field of rights. Topical issues of general legal terminology, which require sharp application and application of professional vocabulary, are considered.

Key words and phrases: Vocabulary of students, terminology, professional terminology, prevention inspector, academic failure, dictionary.

A special condition for the emergence and development of a professional orientation, and then the formation of a specialist, is an interest in educational subjects of a special cycle.[2]

Knowledge of professional terminology is one of the components of the professional competence of specialists of any profile. The term offense has become widespread today. In the explanatory dictionary of Ozhegov, the following definitions are given to the terms:

- Offense, -I, cf. (Official). violation of the law, existing laws, crime. Crime prevention. (Ozhegov S.I. - p.468)
- Prevention, -and, well. A set of preventive measures (Ozhegov S.I. - p. 510)

How many terms should a student learn in the course of studying professional terminology for crime prevention and public safety? It is difficult to answer this question exactly, but an approximate idea of the number of terms that a student should be able to operate with, the content of which will be further deepened, can be made on the basis of textbooks. Today, the ability to use professional terminology provides basic and practical professional training in the field of jurisprudence.

Now knowledge of professional terminology is one of the important requirements for the training of legal personnel in a specialized specialty.

The most important condition for the emergence and development of a professional orientation, and then the formation of a specialist, is an interest in academic subjects of a special cycle, the use of new forms, programs and promising initiatives that contribute to the development of higher legal education, is the effective implementation of the results of scientific developments in lawmaking. Especially improving the skills of students and law enforcement practice, for work and interaction with the population and with the media.

An employee of the internal affairs bodies in the field of crime prevention is obliged to comply with ethical standards, to show correctness in statements. [4]

With the help of modern methods and means, the teacher of the Russian language must change the employee into a competent professional.[8]

The ability to arouse interest in the subject is the great merit of the teacher. Training and retraining of teaching staff using modern forms and methods, information and communication technologies aimed at ensuring a close connection between theoretical training and law enforcement activities, creating an effective system of psychological training, improving the legal, political culture and legal awareness of students largely depends on the teacher. Even the most significant goals lose their attractiveness if the learning process does not give pleasure to the student, causes boredom, does not bring happiness in knowing oneself and the world around. The personality of the teacher should be an example for the students. He must be a teacher and a psychologist, a creator, a creator, a scientific researcher, a purposeful initiator, in a certain sense an actor, modest, benevolent, responsible, active, executive, demanding, fair. A lesson held at a high level influences the formation of high spirituality and moral convictions among students. Therefore, the scientific potential of the teacher, his professional erudition, love for the cause of educating young people, pedagogical skills should be manifested from the first training sessions.

Everyone needs to instill a taste for good speech and an aversion to illiterate speech. This is the minimum that every prevention inspector should work on. [18]

The breadth of erudition, the originality of the presentation of the material allows students to correctly navigate the subject and overcome the difficulties that arise in the process of cognitive activity. An excellent help in this can be teaching aids and visual teaching aids, terminological dictionaries, slides, posters, tables, diagrams that students not only view, but also comment out loud. The vocabulary of students increases when they get acquainted with special professional terminology in practice by solving tasks. *For example:*

**Task 1.* Read the words and explain their meaning. When difficulties refer to dictionaries. *Criminal Code, criminal liability, crime, cumulative crimes, guilt, intentional crime, complicity, punishment, correctional labor, restriction of liberty, deprivation of liberty, confiscation of property, mitigating circumstances, aggravating circumstances, parole, passion, causing harm through negligence .*

**Task 2.* Translate these words into Uzbek.

Crime, deed, evidence, action, inaction, act, deed, behavior, activity, infringement, property, law, order, law, norm, hypothesis, sanction, witness, wrongfulness, guilt, punish ability, damage, intent.

**Task 3.* Find synonyms and antonyms (if any) for the following words. If necessary, use linguistic and special legal dictionaries.

Accuse, insult, fool, retribution, slander, criminal, argue, witness, amateur, exhaustive, tactful, secret, convincing, exclusive, adequate, verdict, identical, export. *Assignment. Read the words and phrases. Explain their meaning. In case of difficulty, refer to terminological dictionaries. Court, judge, judiciary, judiciary, specialized court, bailiff, bailiff, court of first instance, judicial, verdict, court session, trial, chairman of the court, district court, city court, regional court, economic court, administrative court, military court, civil court, Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, state bailiff, trial, justice, witness, testimony.*

Therefore, terminology, which has now become the object of standardization, requires increased attention from not only the content and logical, but also linguistic. With the help of terminology, the learning process is simplified and the generalization and transfer of experience is facilitated. It contributes to a more correct and accurate presentation of programs, textbooks and teaching aids, helps teachers and students to better understand each other and communicate competently.

The results of the conducted research confirmed that one of the reasons for the failure of students is the narrowness of communication and ignorance of professional terms; passivity, as a result of a lack of positive interests; isolation of the student in the study group, his lack of involvement in the life of the team, caused by imperfect communication techniques, the student's inability to come to terms with his other possibilities in communication are a source of constant emotional stress. That is why the value of each word of the teacher is high. The teacher should not allow students to be careless in speech: fuzzy expression of thoughts, switching to tongue twisters, violations of the grammatical constructions of sentences. It is necessary to constantly accustom students to think over the forms of expression of thoughts and appeals. Even the exchange of greetings at the beginning of our classes should be mutually benevolent, calm, polite - disciplining, educating. Tone means a lot. It gives expressiveness of speech, gives emotional coloring to words and phrases. The tone can be solemn, festive, sincere, joyful, upset, angry, sad, sympathetic, cheerful. Sometimes you have to often make a remark to screaming students and ask to increase the voice of those who are too quiet, unsure of themselves, especially those who do not know Russian well. The teacher needs to quickly include all students in communication, while revealing knowledge, views, attitudes, judgments. Dialogues, business disputes are held on various occasions. The word has the greatest value in contacts between a teacher and a student. With its help, the teacher explains, instructs, corrects and enhances learning outcomes. He is obliged to always monitor his speech, to be a model for students. All his actions must be objective and meaningful.

In the efficiency of assimilation of these concepts in the classroom at the Specialized Branch of the State Law University, the presentation, the living word, helps teachers, which, together with other qualities, gives an undeniable positive developmental result. A modern occupation, along with all of the above, must constantly include something new. After all, monotonous actions are unlikely to be able to keep the interest of students today.

Thus, summing up, we can say that today's teacher should become an organizer of activities that guide students to the goal.[9]

In the pedagogical process, the personality of the teacher has been and remains that unique factor, without which it is impossible to achieve success. That is why the teacher should strive to master the skill of conveying to students briefly, in a few phrases, the essence of the task or situation and constantly unobtrusively include students in the work on the development of speech, with special professional terminology.

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